

ANALYSIS OF COMPUTER PROGRAMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ECONOMIC COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article describes a description of computer programs for analysis, forecasting and planning of enterprise activities. Computer programs and their functionality were also mentioned, which should be taught to professors when preparing economics students for future professional activities in the subjects "Statistics", "Econometrics", "Economic Analysis" and other subjects. The article, using computer programs, shows such concepts as determining the current financial situation of enterprises, forecasting their harmless operation, analyzing the need for financing and lending, making certain management decisions, and building predictive models.*

Key words: *computer programs, simulation modeling, enterprise liquidity, financial strategy matrix.*

INTRODUCTION Nowadays, information and all situations related to it are the main source of our society. All human activities in the field of small business and entrepreneurship are inextricably linked with a large amount of information. The abundance of information flows often prevents a person from understanding a large amount of data, analyzing the results obtained and making the right decision based on them. Therefore, there are discussions about analyzing information and developing tools that help create effective solutions based on this analysis or effectively use existing ones. These tools include computer programs for analyzing, forecasting and planning business operations.

Computer programs closely help a person to understand a large amount of information, through their analysis, determine what is necessary, and correctly formulate a strategy for their activities [5]. There are many similar programs today, and in this article we will look at the most popular of them.

LITERARY ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY. The first program we'll look at is Project Expert. This is a very common program that stands out among others for its functionality and ease of use. This is a simulation modeling system that allows you to accurately and competently plan any business decision.

Simulation modeling is a method for studying objects based on the fact that the object being studied is replaced by a simulating one. In this case, experiments are carried out on a modeling object without reference to experiments on a real object, and as a result, information about the object under study is obtained [4].

The functionality of the Project Expert software is as follows:

- development of a business plan for an enterprise;
- calculating the effectiveness of business plans and investment projects using various methods and indicators of economic, financial and statistical analysis;
- analysis of the influence of various factors on the activities of the enterprise;
- development of financial statements and forecasts.

The program is suitable for enterprises engaged in any field of activity. The presence of any analysis, modeling and forecasting tools that allow you to plan business decisions without financial losses has made the Project Expert program one of the leaders in its field [3].

The second program we'll look at is Eviews. This software product includes many econometric analysis methods. This program is more complex than the previous one and requires certain knowledge in the field of mathematical statistics. Eviews has the following features:

- analysis of scientific information;
- calculation of financial analysis indicators;
- construction of various mathematical and economic models of activity;
- analysis and forecasting of market relations;
- calculation of many economic, financial and statistical indicators.

Using this software package, you can determine the presence of statistical connections between the analyzed data and, using the obtained connections, predict the indicators being studied. Despite the simplicity of the EViews program, its graphical capabilities provide all the main data presentation formats (graphs, charts, etc.) for the successful work of analysts, researchers, and marketers. In general, the program only analyzes various models and business decisions are made based on this [1].

The next program that should be considered is the Alt-Forecast software product. The program creates a working enterprise model that reflects all key aspects. This model fully describes all types of enterprise products, their prices, costs and

investments. Such indicators make it possible to optimize all types of enterprise products.

The functionality of this software is as follows:

- determination and analysis of the current financial position of the enterprise;
- determining the harmlessness of the activity for the enterprise;
- analysis of financing and lending needs;
- building predictive models of enterprise development with the adoption of certain management decisions.

The advantage of this program is its ease of use, clarity, and the fact that it is a domestic product that fully takes into account all the economic indicators of the Russian state.

The next program is “Inek-Analyst”. This is one of the oldest software tools in the field of financial analysis, allowing for a comprehensive analysis of the financial and economic activities of an enterprise using the following functions:

- analysis of enterprise performance indicators using various methods;
- forecasting possible bankruptcy of an enterprise;
- analysis of the efficiency of using enterprise resources;
- drawing up a business plan and forecasting the results of its implementation in various conditions;
- analysis of the actual performance of the enterprise, etc.

In general, the program is a very powerful software package that allows you to analyze in detail any area of the company’s activities thanks to its powerful methodological content.

The last program we’ll look at is Audit Expert. This program is designed to study and control the financial position of an enterprise and is a tool for comprehensive financial analysis of the enterprise. The operating principle of the Expert Audit is based on working with the financial statements of the enterprise. In this case, the following functions are implemented:

- conducting various types of financial data analysis;
- assessment of the enterprise’s future financial risks, its liquidity and creditworthiness;
- drawing up forecasts for the development of various financial indicators of the enterprise;
- create a matrix of financial strategies;
- assessment of the reliability of the enterprise’s counterparties.

A company’s liquidity is its ability to pay off its debts quickly and profitably. The level of liquidity is determined by the ratio of assets and liabilities of the balance

sheet and determines the stability of the enterprise. Liquid assets of an enterprise are all assets that can be converted into cash and used to pay off debts [6].

The financial strategy matrix is a representation of the strategic model using the three main categories of financial management. Them:

result of economic activity;

the result of financial activities;

the result of financial and economic activities [2].

In general, the Audit Expert program is a very necessary software tool for financial planning and increasing the financial stability of an enterprise. It is believed that all of these programs have sufficient functionality to solve a wide range of problems.

CONCLUSION. In collaboration with Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Tashkent State Economic University, the scientific program of science “Econometrics” was approved in 2023 in the educational direction 60310100-Economics (by industry and sector). Based on the approved scientific program, teachers taught students the modernization of the economics of enterprises, the implementation of decision-making processes, the effective use of econometric methods and models and modern information technologies in the analysis of their economic indicators [7].

Taking into account the above, we can say that in higher education, professors and teachers integrate economic disciplines with the help of information technology, improve the quality and efficiency of education, and effectively organize the future professional activities of students.

REFERENCES

1. Сулопов Б.М. ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ МОБИЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКЕ СТУДЕНТОВ. <https://www.interscience.uz/index.php/home/article/view/136>
2. Сулопов Б.М. ТАЪЛИМДА ДАСТУРИЙ ПАКЕТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ.
3. Сулопов Б.М. ТАЛАБАЛАРНИ КАСБИЙ ФАОЛИЯТГА ТАЙЁРЛАШДА ЭКОНОМЕТРИКА ВА АХБОРОТ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИ ФАНЛАРАРО ИНТЕГРАЦИЯСИДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/talabalarni-kasbiy-faoliyatga-tayyorlashda-ekonometrika-va-ahborot-tehnologiyalari-fanlararo-integratsiyasidan-foydalanish>
4. Сулопов Б.М. Замонавий иқтисодийда ахборот технологияларнинг ўрни. Интернаука. № 4-2, 2017, с 61-62.
5. Сулопов Б.М. Формирование инновационной деятельности студентов с использованием программных продуктов. Проблемы современного образования, № 6, 2020, с 206-212. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/formirovanie-innovatsionnoy-deyatelnosti-studentov-s-ispolzovaniem-programmnyh-produktov>
6. Сулопов Б.М. Информатикани ўқитишда фалсафий муаммолар ва илмий билиш. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/informatikani-itishda-falsafiy-muammolar-va-ilmiy-bilish>
7. Сулопов Б.М. ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА КОМПЬЮТЕРНЫХ ПРОГРАММ В ОБЛАСТИ АНАЛИЗА, ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЯ И ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯ. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/harakteristika-kompyuternyh-programm-v-oblasti-analiza-prognozirovaniya-i-planirovaniya-deyatelnosti-predpriyatiya>